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Valerie Joy D. Magbiro

Valuing Ecological Threats of Renewable Energy Facilities in Aklan:
Wind Farm and Hydropower Plant

Thesis Adviser:

DR. RAMIRO F. PLOPINO
Faculty of Management and Development Studies

03 June 2022

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RAMIRO F. PLOPINO
Faculty-in-Charge, ENRM 290 (Special Problem)

(Date)

CONSUELO D.L. HABITO
Program Chair, Master of Environment and
Natural Resources Management

16 January 2023

(Date)

JOANE V. SERRANO
Dean
Faculty of Management and Development Studies

17 January 2023

(Date)

BIOGRAPHICAL SKETCH

The author is a Geodetic Engineer in DENR Provincial Environment and Natural Resources Office Aklan since 2015. Previously, she was a geodetic engineer of Makati Development Corporation (2015) and ASEC Development and Construction Corporation (2019-2015). Her first employment was in a private surveying company, R.O. Vasquez Constructions and Surveys from 2005 to 2009. Upon transferring to government service, her interests and awareness related to environment and ecosystems grew. Her exposure to field survey in the Peace and Development Site in Aklan made her enroll in Master of Environment and Natural Resources Management in UP Open University.

She graduated with a B.S. Geodetic Engineering in FEATI University in 2005 with Highest Honors and was a Geodetic Engineers of the Philippines, Inc. (GEPI) Region IV scholar.

The author is the second from the eldest among four children of Mr. Herminio E.de Vera of Bocaue, Bulacan and Mrs. Margarita Lacson de Vera of Talisay City, Negros Occidental. She is married to Engr. Val Raymond delos Santos Magbiro, and is blessed with a beautiful daughter, Dorothy Ann.

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The Department of Environment and Natural Resources DENR which always stands with the truth and reports only the true status and effects of the projects the government implements and introduces to save, conserve and preserve our natural resources while trying to be sustainable for the future and resilient with today's changes.

The electric and power sector of the Philippines which studies the feasibilities of all renewable energies the Philippines can explore reducing environment impacts as well as the costs that every Filipino family pays for.

DECLARATION

This is to certify that:

- I. The special problem comprises only my original work towards the MENRM except where indicated in the Preface
- II. Due acknowledgement has been made in the text to all other material used
- III. The special problem is fewer than 25 000 words in length, exclusive of tables, maps, bibliographies and appendices

Valerie Joy D. Magbiro

TABLE OF CONTENTS

TITLE PAGE	i
UNIVERSITY PERMISSION	ii
APPROVAL PAGE	iii
BIOGRAPHICAL SKETCH	iv
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	v
DEDICATION	vi
DECLARATION	vii
TABLE OF CONTENTS	viii
LIST OF TABLES	x
LIST OF FIGURES	xi
LIST OF PLATES	xii
LIST OF APPENDICES	xiii
LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS	xiv
ABSTRACT	xv
CHAPTER 1. INTRODUCTION	17
Objectives	20
Theoretical Framework	21
Conceptual Framework	22
CHAPTER 2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE	23
Political Status of Philippine Renewable Energies	23
Wind Farm	24
Hydropower Plant	25
CHAPTER 3. METHODS	29
Spatial Analysis Using GIS	29
Landscape Patterns	30
Quantifying Patch Richness	30
Multi-Level Scale Model	31
Plant Scale	31

River Scale	32
Watershed	32
Correlation Analysis	35
Test Value (<i>t-test</i>)	36
Interviews and Questionnaires	36
Areas of Study	37
CHAPTER 4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION	38
Data Quality and Assumptions	38
By Using Land Cover Map and Satellite Images	38
Patch Richness	41
Analysis on Affectivity of Technological Interventions	45
DTBird	45
Fishway	47
Evaluation of ecological impacts using Multi-Scale Model	51
Correlation Coefficient	56
t-Test for the significant difference between declared area and the actual area affected by ecological threats	56
Socio-Economic Review	58
CHAPTER 5. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS	62
CHAPTER 6. RECOMMENDATIONS	63
REFERENCES	64
APPENDICES	68

LIST OF TABLES

<u>TABLE</u>		<u>PAGE</u>
1	Scale of Correlation Coefficient and its Corresponding Values	36
2	Patch Richness of Wind Farm in Nabas, Aklan	41
3	Patch Richness of Hydropower plant in Madalag, Aklan	43
4	Values of ecological threats of wind farm and hydropower plant in million pesos	55
5	Values considered for t-test for hydropower plant and wind farm	56
6	Measures of central tendency and variation for <i>t</i> -test	56
7	Awarded hydropower projects as of June 2020 in the province of Aklan	61

LIST OF FIGURES

<u>FIGURE</u>		<u>PAGE</u>
1	Theoretical Framework of Renewable Energy development facilities in Multi-level scale affecting environment	21
2	Conceptual Framework of Renewable Energy development facilities in multi-level scales affecting environment	22
3	Sample diagram of wind farm	25
4	A schematic sample of a small run-of-river project	26
5	Indicators of multi-scale ecological loss	31
6	Enlarged Map of Panay Island showing the location of Wind Farm in Nabas and Malay, and the Hydropower Plant in Madalag, Aklan	37
7	Land Cover Map 2015 Highlighting the NPPNP	40
8	Shape files of fragmented landscape of wind farm area in Nabas and Malay, Aklan generated using CAD and ArcGIS	40
9	Overlaid patches of Timbaban Hydropower Plant in Land Cover Map 2015	42
10	Extent of the Access Road Development, and Other Construction Facilities for Timbaban Hydropower Plant in Madalag, Aklan	43
11	Schematic drawing of a vertical slot fishway	47
12	Bar Chart comparing the Timbaban hydropower plant and Nabas Wind farm on areas actual affected and declared in hectares and the technology applied in million pesos	50
13	Graph comparing the two RE facilities' effects to environment at different scales in million pesos	55
14	Critical and test values of the significance in difference of both RE facilities on declared areas vs. computed area using GIS tools	57

LIST OF PLATES

<u>PLATE</u>		<u>PAGE</u>
1	The Northwest Panay Peninsula Natural Park adjacent to Petrowind wind farm in Nabas, Aklan	19
2	Aerial photo of the area affected by the development of wind farm in Nabas, Malay, Aklan	39
3	Terrestrial photo of the area affected by the development of wind farm in Nabas, Malay, Aklan	39
4	Satellite image of portion of Panay Island showing the location of Northwest Panay Peninsula Natural Park	39
5	Photo collage of Flora and Fauna within wind farm and Northwest Panay Peninsula Natural Park	41
6	Satellite image of area where access roads and Other development occurred in Maria Cristina, Madalag, Aklan	42
7 & 8	Liktinon White Rocks in Brgy. Maria Cristina, Madalag, Aklan is part of Aklan River Watershed Forest Reserve	44
9	Overlooking Boracay from Nabas wind farms' turbines in Nabas and Malay Aklan	46
10	The PWEI Wind Farm in Nabas and Malay Aklan is between the Northwest Panay Peninsula Natural Park and Boracay Island	46
11	Original Perspective of fishway at the weir	47
12	Actual Implementation of fishway	47
13	Photo collage of meeting with the OEPGC Staff during tunnel construction and the built powerhouse	48
14	Pawa Nabas Elementary School located within the PWEI's wind farm with signage campaign not to cut more trees	58
15	Overlooking Nabas wind farm's turbines from Boracay Island taken on March 10, 2020	59

LIST OF APPENDICES

<u>APPENDIX</u>		<u>PAGE</u>
A	Salient Features of RA 9513, “Renewable Energy Act of 2008”	68
B	Sample Survey Questionnaire	70
C	Table of Critical Values for <i>t</i> -test	72

LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

ASEAN	Association of South East Asian Nations
CAD	Computer Aided Design
CEA	Cumulative Effect Assessment
DENR	Department of Environment and Natural Resources
DOE	Department of Energy
EIA	Environmental Impact Assessment
ENIPAS	Expanded National Protected Areas
EPIRA	Electric Power Industry Reform Act
ET	Energy Transition
FLAg	Forest Land Use Agreement
GA	Genetic Algorithm
GHG	Green House Gas
GIS	Geographic Information System
IPBES	Policy Platform for Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCOE	Levelised Cost of Energy
MPL	Multi-level decision-making Perspective
NAMRIA	National Mapping and Resource Information Authority
NGP	National Greening Program
NIPAS	National Integrated Protected Areas System
NPP	Net Primary Production
NPPNP	Northwest Panay Peninsula Natural Park
OEPGC	Oriental Energy Power Generation Corporation
PAMB	Protected Area Management Board
PWEI	PetroWind Energy Incorporated
RE	Renewable Energy
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
TCAGP	Training Center for Applied Geodesy and Photogrammetry
UTM	Universal Transverse Mercator
VEC	Valued Ecosystems Component
WGS	World Geodetic System
WTG	Wind Turbine Generator

ABSTRACT

MAGBIRO, VALERIE JOY DE VERA. Master of Environment and Natural Resources Management, Faculty of Management and Development Studies. University of the Philippines Open University. May 2022. **Valuing Ecological Threats of Renewable Energy Facilities in Aklan: Wind Farm and Hydropower Plant.**

Special Problem Adviser: Dr. Ramiro F. Plopino

Resorting to renewable energies is one of the strategies that are being adapted globally to supply the increasing demand with “less” negative effects to environment. New trends of gadgets in the markets are changing every minute, thus requiring more and more power to generate in consonance with the growing population. This study is intended to assess the biophysical, social and economic value (in monetary worth) the damages/loss to environment caused by hydropower development and wind energy systems in Aklan despite all the positive reviews on renewable energies, giving the world a new “hope” for sustainable future. The researcher describes the two (2) RE systems: (1) the 36-Megawatt Nabas Wind Power Project of PetroWind Energy Incorporated (PWEI) located in Brgys. Pawa, Unidos, Rizal and Napaan in municipalities of Nabas and Malay and (2) the 18-MW Timbaban Hydropower Project of Oriental Energy and Power Generation Corporation (OEPGC) in Brgy. Maria Cristina, Madalag, Aklan. In doing so, determining their impacts on immediate environment is made possible. Conservation projects incorporated in their FLAg’s are evaluated whether intervention compensates the damages incur to environment or not. While doing the research, the author observes obscurity and reluctance from both renewable energy companies in providing data, thus resorting to secondary ones. However, biophysical assessment was done by using Land Cover Maps and GIS tools observing the patch richness and habitat fragmentation. Ecological impacts in plant, river and watershed levels were measured using Multi Scale Model Framework of X.J.Li, et al. (2015). Impacts on social and economic aspects were described based on interviews among stakeholders and local residents adjoining RE facilities. Descriptive and inferential statistical tools are also used in determining the significance of the scale of ecological impacts caused by RE systems. Integrating all facets of environment, political aspect plays major role in defining the requirements and

limitations which govern RE systems. A policy proposal to ensure the effectiveness of mitigating measures and conservation efforts made by or to be undertaken by any RE developer is recommended by the author.

Keywords: renewable energy, ecological threats, wind farm, hydropower plant, sustainable, environment

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

Studying the energy being used daily, how it works, where it comes from, how long will it sustain man's need or defining the limit to use it as a resource is very important. Fossil fuels as energy resources such as coal, oils and natural gas can be more harmful to the environment compare to renewable energies. Nowadays that climate change is real anywhere in the world, investing in renewable energies is most expedient for most energy suppliers because of its sustainability. However, these renewable energy facilities have environmental infliction and most of the measures of the impacts include air and water pollution, danger to public health, water use, land use, habitat and wildlife loss and undeniably, global warming emissions. These impacts are given very little attention which others consider "tolerable" and to many, even "invisible."

Ecosystem services are technically difficult and expensive to measure. Intrinsic, instrumental and relational values are not easy to combine. A comprehensive valuation which can include a combination of unidimensional methods of valuation and/or adopt integrated approaches in capturing plural values is now evolving. The Intergovernmental Science – Policy Platform for Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES) is currently undertaking a methodological assessment regarding the diverse conceptualization of multiple values of nature and its contributions, including biodiversity and ecosystem functions and services (Subramanian, Yiu, Dasgupta, et al., 2019). To make it clear, "valuing" or "valuation" in this paper does not only entail "economic value" but also stands as proxy for socio-ecological and political aspects of RE developments as these factors are interrelated and interconnected in an "ecosystem." To make it simple, all values accounted are measured and expressed in monetary terms.

Ecological threats involve human activities or natural phenomena that affect different ecosystems, directly or indirectly every living organism in each system that leads to chaos. Climate change is at the top of the list. Floods, heat waves, droughts, storms, decrease in crop yields, and rising sea levels due to greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions brought by human activities are just some of the effects we're seeing from

climate change. Air pollution and wastes poison soil and waterways, kill plants and animals and harm humans. Overgrazing deteriorates the soil and deforestation cause habitat and biodiversity loss. Overpopulation results to urban sprawl, more infrastructures, and more wildernesses are taken over, more pollution is created. Overfishing makes extinction of many species of fish in the ocean. As you may have noticed, most of the threats have the prefix “over.” This paper wants to check if this prefix is present in both hydropower plant and wind farm facilities development—that is valuing threats of renewable energy facilities by studying the different impacts of previous samples at different spatial scales which led to ecological loss.

The perception of renewable energy resources as a “clean” or “less harmful” vis a vis environmental impacts was challenged by Abbasi and Abbasi (2000). But this definition was corrected by Ardente, et al. (2006) as the “cleaner” than ones based on fossil fuel conversion. According to them, wind energy facilities or wind farm is the least harmful among several RE developments. The largest environmental impacts caused by an Italian wind farm, for example are mainly due to the manufacturing of wind turbines and building works using Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and energy performances (Ardente, et al 2006). Other impacts are not significant. Meanwhile, hydropower plants have numerous reviews, debates and case studies in journal articles in terms of adverse environmental impacts especially that they affect one of the precious natural resources— Water!

Two years ago, the DENR released Administrative Order No. 2019-05 or the Implementing Rules and Regulations of R.A. 7586 (NIPAS Act of 1992) as amended by ENIPAs of 2018 or RA 11038. Under section 14 of the IRR, *“renewable energy projects maybe allowed within the protected area by the PAMB with the concurrence of the DENR Secretary with the provision that the renewable energy projects shall be located outside the strict protection zones, shall undergo the EIA and shall adopt reduced impact technologies so as not to be detrimental to ecosystem functions, biodiversity, cultural practices and traditions.”* Related to this, the Nabas Wind Farm has applied for expansion which might encroach the Northwest Panay Peninsula Natural Park (NPPNP), one of the newly established as “protected areas within the classification of national park” pursuant to the Philippine Constitution according to the Licensing Unit of Provincial Environment and Natural Resources Office.

Plate 1. The Northwest Panay Peninsula Natural Park adjacent to Petrowind wind farm in Nabas, Aklan.

SOURCE: Magbiro, 2020

None compliance with the requirement by the DENR in planting trees equivalent for a single tree cut prior to facility construction in allocated areas with the ratio of 1:10 is one of the problems that enforcement and implementing agency encounters on these supposedly “sustainable” energy goal of the country in line with the SDG 7 Target 7.2. “Increase the global percentage of renewable energy.”

The Timbaban Hydropower plant in Madalag had encroached NGP sites and had destroyed 2.3 hectares and affected 1,500 IP members in the municipality.

Objectives

Estimating the monetary worth of ecological threats is the main objective of this paper. The author used “valuing” which connotes “assessing,” “evaluating” or “appraising” as to easily answer “*how much*” and giving value or importance to these threats that have cost/damages in upland environment area surrounding the Renewable Energy facilities as well as the lowland community so as not to be ignored by stakeholders. Construction of RE facilities itself is already a threat. This threat has negative impacts on its surrounding community. In the long run, while maintaining these facilities during its operation, ecological loss or degradation of landscape and ecosystem will be realized. The impact is ecological loss. These losses can be assessed by: (1) Quantifying the area affected by these facilities with spatial analysis using Geographic Information System (GIS), (2) identifying landscape patterns and quantifying patch richness by comparing the before and after condition of forest cover using temporal points, (3) analyzing the effectivity of technological interventions, (4) measure the impacts using Multi-level scale model and (5) comparing the significant difference between the declared area of RE developers against the actual area affected by constructed facilities/development. The author assumed that ecological threat is directly proportional to ecological impact and ecological impact is equal to ecological loss as well. That is:

Ecological threat = ecological impact = ecological loss (degradation).

Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Theoretical Framework of Renewable Energy development facilities in Multi-level scale affecting environment.

Figure 2. Conceptual Framework of Renewable Energy development facilities in multi-level scales affecting environment.

CHAPTER 2

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Political Status of Philippine's Renewable Energy

The Philippines has targeted to triple its renewable energy generation capacity to 15,304 MW by 2030 and has also recently joined other ASEAN members in committing to having 23% of their energy supply from renewable resources by 2025 (Farley and Williams, 2018). Even The Philippine Energy Plan Road map of DOE intends to increase the RE installed capacity to at least 20 000 MW by 2040. Republic Act 9136 or the “Electric Power Industry Reform Act” aimed to reduce the power cost and secure the country’s energy supply. In the study of Saculsan (2018), she pointed out that EPIRA Law has failed. Philippines is still one of the highest paying countries in Asia when it comes to electricity rates. With the use of multi-level decision-making perspective (MPL) of energy transition (ET) theory, she had enumerated different challenges that the RE sector in the Philippines faces. Historically, the government had made several mistakes that led to power crises in the past. To prevent that from happening again, its energy policy anchors only on “energy security.” Sustainability perspective is out of the picture. Though it has brought a positive effect in welcoming RE developments in the energy portfolio of the country, energy security was only viewed as the “increase in generation capacity.” The negative effect is that it led to expansion of conventional energies because as of now the country still importing 76% of the total energy and worse, it has paved the way for monopoly/oligopoly. In short, EPIRA Law just highlighted the constraints to the RE sector.

Kardooni, R., et al. (2015) examined the experts’ perceptions and understanding of the renewable energy development in Malaysia. They employed multi aspect investigation of potential technological, economic, social or political barriers to RE development in the country. The target to use RE is influenced by the cost of renewable energy technology based on their findings. Thus, concluded that in order to overcome these barriers, the government should play a powerful leadership.

However, in the published work of Shania, N. Et al. (2020), they concluded that there is no longer a need to choose “affordable” or “clean”, but rather affordable “AND” clean energy are now feasible aside from being urgent among ASEAN Member States

(AMS). They have commended the Philippines in phasing out majority of the fossil-fuel subsidies. Instead, developing a national social safety net by expanding electrification program and encourage investments more in renewable energy is being exercised by introducing incentives. On the other hand, still fossil-fuel based is the most affordable energy in Asia. To be able to keep longer vision, continuous assessment on energy strategies and policies must be done by evaluating what works and what does not. Inclusiveness was also highlighted in their recommendations which suggest designing fair policies in giving subsidies and incentives that will benefit the communities or sectors that need them the most.

Wind farm

Black (1998) discussed wind farm and wind energy in the following manner:
Wind farms capture the energy of wind flow by using turbines and converting it into electricity. Wind energy is a clean energy source, which means that it doesn't pollute the air like other forms of energy. Wind energy doesn't produce carbon dioxide, or release any harmful products that can cause environmental degradation or negatively affect human health like smog, acid rain, or other heat-trapping gases. Since wind farms tend to be built in rural or remote areas, they are usually far from bustling cities where the electricity is needed most. However, the National Research Council, Washington D.C. 2007 made a deeper investigation citing the building wind-energy installations with large numbers of turbines can disrupt landscapes and habitats, and the rotating turbine blades sometimes kill birds and bats. They also organized the environmental impact assessments into three-dimensional axes such as spatial jurisdiction (local/regional), project stages (pre-project, construction, operational and post-operational) and environmental and human impacts.

In a centralised system, (Abassi, S.A. & Abassi, N., 2000), wind generation reduces wind-speed which cause stress to ecosystem as well as interfere with habitats and bird flights. Other than that, it creates noise pollution and aesthetic degradation on land cover. Soil moisture is possible to increase for areas adjacent to windmills. Because of reduced evaporation from their surface, lakes that are downhill from the windmills might become warmer.

Allam (2019) proposed a method in optimization of energy generation in wind farm with minimal impacts on flora and fauna. He used numeric Genetic Algorithm (GA) to determine optimal sites of turbines and the Levelised Cost of Energy (LCOE) including the pathways of migratory birds so as to preserve fragile ecosystems.

Figure 3. Sample diagram of wind farm. (Source:Wind power, 2017)

Hydropower plant

Dams are what people most associate to when it comes to hydroelectric power. Water flows through the dam's turbines to produce electricity, known as pumped-storage hydropower. Run-of-river hydropower uses a channel to funnel water through rather than powering it through a dam. Although hydroelectric power does not pollute the air, it disrupts waterways and negatively affects the animals that live in them, changing water levels, currents, and migration paths for many fish and other freshwater ecosystems. (Black, 2018). O.Tamm & T. Tamm (2020) calculated the capacity of a small hydropower run-of-river plant using GIS. They categorized four types of potentials in RE studies: 1.) theoretical (natural energy), 2.) technical (energy that can be utilized with the existing technology), 3.) exploitable (negative environmental impacts) and 4.) economic (financially beneficial if utilized). It was cited also that most RE assessment studies focused on the first two potentials as the exploitable and economic potential are highly location dependent and require in-dept analysis at each potential site.

Figure 4. A schematic sample of a small run-of-river project. (Source: LRES Capstone, 2014)

A small run-of-the-river hydropower projects maybe consider to have minimal effects on the environment. For larger one, a ladder or fishway is required. Dissolved gases downstream may affect fish due to diversion of large amounts of water that reduces river flows. This affects water velocity and depth which decrease habitat quality for fish and aquatic organisms. As a result, reduced flows can lead to excessively warm water for fishes during summer.

Valuation of Ecological Threats

Locally, vulnerability assessment and watershed characterization are widely and currently being implemented by the Department and Environment and Natural Resources (DENR) using Geographic and Information System (GIS) and remote sensing to support sustainable management of watersheds in the country. This provides managers and decision makers basis for conservation strategies and apply appropriate development in the area (DENR, FMB). To be able for private companies to secure Environmental Compliance Certificate (ECC) for their proposed projects, the Environmental Management Bureau (EMB) will require Environment Impact Assessment (EIA)—which now they incorporated the Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR)

and Climate Change Adaptation (CCA) (DMC, 2011-005). Its purpose is to facilitate review of the projects and its implementation by incorporating international best practices and provide enhanced standards customized for specific industry types EIA Reports. Last year, the government has just rolled out the Philippine, Illegal, Unreported and Unregulated (IUU) Fishing Index and Threat Assessment Tool (I-FIT) to DENR Regional and Field Offices. This includes the setting up of national baseline of IUU fishing that can be compared across target areas in a standard way and track progress in reducing the IUU overtime. Its purpose is for the assessment, planning and implementation of long term solutions to threats to biodiversity and the coastal and marine environment (BMB). On the other hand, the Mines and Geoscience Bureau (MGB) has been implementing the National Geohazard Assessment and Mapping Program to identify the areas in the country that are susceptible or prone to various geologic hazard and provide necessary information to various stakeholders in order to lessen or mitigate the impacts of different geohazards, particularly on landslides and floods (MGB). There is also the Groundwater Resource Assessment which is used to determine the availability of groundwater resources and the threats to contamination and depletion. This covers two (2) aspects, the resource assessment and the vulnerability component (DENR).

Internationally, Knaus, et al. (2006) used the Ecological Footprint (EF) concept to calculate the total land use of projects with indirect monetary valuation of environmental impacts. They cited the difficulty in economic analysis in identifying the complete range of costs and benefits and placing a monetary value on them as some private goods does not reflect the “environmental fair price” and the full cost of environmental degradation. Direct or indirect proxies for valuing environmental impacts (such as land prices, trees cut, etc) are used if no market price exists. If no proxies available at all, the consumers’ “willingness to pay (WTP) or “willingness to accept (WTA) are being used. However, the EF is an attempt to quantify sustainability which is based on the fact that every human activity has an impact on the environment through the resources required by these activities and the wastes generated from them.

A novel approach using EIA methodology was used to identify and assess social-ecological outcomes from civic ecology interventions study by Davids and Slotow (2022). They quantified the impact significance of six civic (community led) interventions implemented by a local community programs such as solid waste

management, water quality monitoring, invasive alien plant control, crop production, recycling and community engagement. This provides the practitioners an intervention quantifying tool to select optimal local management interventions that can be aligned with desired outcomes related to specific community challenges and policy requirements.

Archetype analysis was used by Romero and Cabello (2021) to address social-ecological complexity of landscape change. This involved the inductive detection of typical social-ecological systems and changes therein and the interpretation with deductive types of human-nature connectedness. It provides detection and mapping of key sustainability challenges due to changes in social-ecological systems (SESs). Integrating the inductive (bottom up) and deductive (top down) approaches was also applied by Evans, N.M., et al., (2019) in the assessment for landscape conservation through iterative, multi-level assessments. The comprehensive threat assessment across Colorado River basin in North America by Comte, et al. (2022) was presented using a spatial framework accounting for the wide range of human activities and spatial extent of influence known to affect the ecological integrity of riverine ecosystems. The result showed that threat indices used were correlated with biological, chemical, hydrological and physical indicators of ecological.

CHAPTER 3

METHODS

Spatial Analysis Using GIS

For biophysical assessment, Spatial Analysis using Geographic Information System (GIS), with temporal points of before and after the construction of facilities was employed in weighing the extent of the damage incurred to the environment. This method is second of the five (5) steps under Cumulative Effects Assessment (CEA). In establishing spatial boundaries, it should expand sufficiently to address the cause-effect relationships between actions and Valued Ecosystems Components (VECs) unlike in Environmental Impact Assessments (EIAs), more or less arbitrary local boundaries around sites which are limited to the effects of the single action is being considered. Using jurisdictional borders in defining the study area may seem to be convenient, according to the CEA guidelines. But such approach typically disregards the ecological realities of the area (Hegman, G. et al, 1999). In spatial analysis, the primary objective is to establish temporal boundaries of “how far back in time” and “how far ahead in the future.” Definite units of time are to consider in organizing time-dependent changes in the study area. CEA is also flexible which can go beyond “zone-of-influence” baseline, therefore researchers must be prepared to adjust the boundaries during the assessment process, and likewise being able to defend such changes. The author adopted this methodology in this study instead of the usual EIA’s which is being practiced in the Philippines. EIA focuses only in one or specific project/plan. On the other hand, CEA focuses on the receiving environment and consider all of the effects on a given receptor. Since the author considered two renewable energy facilities in this study, the latter has been applied.

In this study, the National Mapping and Resource Information Authority (NAMRIA) approved Land Cover map was compared to the Land Classification Map and satellite image using Google Earth. They were then overlaid altogether using Computer Aided Design (CAD) and Arc GIS to come up with the area affected by developed access roads and other facilities. The approved Forest Land Use Agreements (FLAg’s) maps of both RE developers were projected using the Universal Transverse Mercator 51N, Luzon 1911 (UTM) datum. These coordinates were then encoded in AutoCAD and converted to shape files using Arc GIS application. The UTM

projection was converted to World Geodetic System 1984 (WGS 84), the reference system for the Global Positioning System (GPS) in latitudes and longitudes in projecting the improvements on each RE facilities such as access roads wind turbines locations, power house, expand of tunnels, etc.

Landscape Patterns

One of the simplest method in analyzing the extent of the development introduced in a landscape is by computing its patch richness. Costanza, et al. (2019) presented a set of perspectives in measurement of landscape patterns through research articles on new and emerging pattern metrics and its applications. Their objective is to highlight the integrated pattern-oriented approaches in which Fischer and Lindenmeyer (2007) defined to habitat fragmentation research. Despite critiques and challenges of landscape pattern measurement, the use of landscape pattern metrics has continued to increase and developed overtime.

Quantifying Patch Richness

This metric is redundant with both patch richness density and relative patch richness. Patch Richness has a formula of:

$$\mathbf{PR = m}$$

where: PR = the number of different patch types present within the landscape boundary.

m = no. of patch types present within the landscape boundary

The range of PR is greater or equals to 1 without limit ($PR \geq 1$) and is unit less.

Figure 5. Indicators of multi-scale ecological loss

Ecological loss evaluation at a plant scale

Environmental pollution

Solid and wastewater pollution during construction for both wind farm and run-of-river hydropower plant maybe estimated using X.J.Li et al. (2015):

$$V_{wp} = \sum V_{wpi}, \quad (1)$$

Where V_{wp} is the value of environmental pollution loss, and V_{wpi} is the cost of investing in construction of the major waste water and solid waste treatment project i (Php).

Soil Erosion

During construction period, soil erosion occurs mainly in soil surface destruction, loss of arable land resources and loss of residual field soil. These maybe estimated from:

$$V_{se} = \sum V_{i0}, \quad (2)$$

Where V_{se} (Php) is the value of soil erosion loss, and V_{i0} is the cost of building a soil and water conservation project i .

Ecological loss evaluation at the river/local scale

For hydropower plant, fish habitat destruction was considered as the Timbaban hydropower plant is a run-of-river without a reservoir to get the volume of bed-load sediment to compute sediment deposition. For wind farm, bird habitat loss will be accounted and estimated using the same method as with fish habitat loss:

$$V_{FD} = \sum V_{FDi}, \quad (\text{For fish habitat loss}) \quad (3)$$

where: V_{FD} (Php) is the loss value of fish habitat destruction and V_{FDi} (Php) is the cost of fish protection project i .

$$V_{BD} = \sum V_{BDi}, \quad (\text{For bird habitat loss}) \quad (4)$$

where: V_{BD} (Php) is the loss value of bird habitat destruction and V_{BDi} (Php) is the cost of bird species protection project i .

Ecological loss evaluation at the watershed scale

Net primary productivity (NPP) loss, carbon fixation and oxygen release loss will be calculated by evaluating inundation by the market price method.

Net Primary Productivity Loss caused by Hydropower plant and Wind Farm

Using the Miami model (Lieth, 1975):

$$NPP_{\text{Rain}(y)} = 3000(1 - e^{-0.000664\text{Rain}(y)}) \quad (5)$$

$$NPP_{\text{Temp}(y)} = \frac{3000}{1 + 1.315 - 0.119 \text{Temp}(y)} \quad (6)$$

$$V_{NPP,j} = \left[\sum_{i=1}^4 (NPP_{ij} \cdot A_{ij}) - \sum_{i=5}^6 (NPP_{ij} \cdot A_{ij}) \cdot T \cdot \varepsilon_{NPP} \cdot P_{\text{coal}} \right] \quad (7)$$

where: Rain (y) is the annual rainfall (mm) and Temp (y) is the annual average temperature (deg C). NPP is expressed in grammes of dry matter per square meter per year. The author will try to adjust the NPP coefficient based on the land cover type in the region.

V_{NPPj} (Php) is the value of net primary productivity loss in region j ; NPP_{ij} (gCm⁻²yr⁻¹) is the net primary productivity reduction per unit area of land cover type i in region j ($i=1,2,\dots,6$)(i.e. forest, cropland, grassland, unused land, water area, and building land); A_{ij} (ha) is the inundation area of land cover type in region j ; T is the operation period of the hydropower project, which is approximately 30 years for Small Hydropower Plants (Varun, et al., 2012); $\bar{\epsilon}_{NPP}$ (%) is the calorific value ratio of standard coal and carbon; and P_{coal} (Php/ton) is the price of standard coal in the Philippines.

NPP or Terrestrial net primary production is the central carbon-related variable summarizing the interface between plant and other processes (Field, et al., 1995). In global scale, it is the most modeled with its ecological parameters used. In this paper, NPP calculation model by Leith (1975) used climate as a function. Others considered calculations of the distribution of the biomes which assumes that NPP is constant across each major biome. (Field, et al., 1995).

Carbon Fixation and oxygen release loss

Using the Market Price Method (Li, et al., 2015):

Since all green plants sequester CO₂ and release O₂, and green plants construction and maintenance need investment, therefore the unit value of CO₂ sequestration and O₂ release depends on the cost of green plants construction and maintenance (Wang, et al., 2010).

$$M_{CO_2} = \left[\sum_{i=1}^4 (NPP_i \cdot A_i) - \sum_{i=5}^6 (NPP_i \cdot A_i) \right] \cdot T \cdot \alpha_{CO_2}, \quad (8)$$

$$M_{O_2} = \left[\sum_{i=1}^4 (NPP_i \cdot A_i) - \sum_{i=5}^6 (NPP_i \cdot A_i) \right] \cdot T \cdot \beta_{O_2}, \quad (9)$$

$$V_{\text{CO}_2\&\text{O}_2} = P_{\text{CO}_2} \cdot M_{\text{CO}_2} + P_{\text{O}_2} \cdot M_{\text{O}_2}, \quad (10)$$

where: $V_{\text{CO}_2\&\text{O}_2}$ (Php) = value of carbon fixation and carbon release loss;

M_{CO_2} and M_{O_2} (g) = loss mass of CO_2 fixation and O_2 release;

P_{CO_2} and P_{O_2} (Php/g) = cost of CO_2 fixation and O_2 release per unit,
based on the afforestation costing method;

α_{CO_2} (g) = mass of carbon dioxide fixed by 1 g of organic matter;

β_{O_2} (g) = mass of O_2 released by 1 g of organic matter

Human habitat loss

According to Li, et al., the monetary value of human habitat loss can be estimated as the cost of compensation for emigrant resettlement, estimated from the value of real estate in the region where the displaced people will be resettled using the recovering expense method:

$$V_{\text{human habitat}} = \text{Pop}_{\text{emigrant}} \cdot A_{\text{house}} \cdot P_{\text{house}} \quad (11)$$

where: $V_{\text{human habitat}}$ (Php) = the value of the loss of human habitat;

$\text{Pop}_{\text{emigrant}}$ (no. of person) = migrating population;

A_{house} (m^2 per capita) = average area of housing per capita in the resettlement place;

P_{house} (Php/ m^2) = house price in the resettled region in any given emigrant year.

Indicator analysis was done for deeper analysis by standardizing the six ecological loss indicators as presented above and their average values were taken according to the scales of the two RE systems.

Correlation Analysis

Determination of significance of the two RE's ecological impacts by getting the correlation coefficients of the two (2) RE systems was done to show the strength of relationships of disturbances/improvement to the mitigating measures applied by each RE facility. Applying Pearson's Correlation Coefficient formula:

$$r = \frac{n(\sum xy) - (\sum x)(\sum y)}{\sqrt{[n\sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2][n\sum y^2 - (\sum y)^2]}}$$

where: r = coefficient

n = number of ordered pairs

x = independent variable

y = dependent variable

$\sum xy$ = sum of the products of ordered pair

$\sum x$ = sum of the independent variables

$\sum y$ = sum of dependent variables

$\sum x^2$ = sum of the squared x independent variables

$\sum y^2$ = sum of the squared y dependent variables

The author was able to conclude the direction of correlation. The table below shows the scale of correlation coefficient and its corresponding interpretation.

Table 1. Scale of Correlation Coefficient and its Corresponding Values

Scale of correlation coefficient	Value
$0 < r \leq 0.19$	Very Low Correlation
$0.2 \leq r \leq 0.39$	Low Correlation
$0.4 \leq r \leq 0.59$	Moderate Correlation
$0.6 \leq r \leq 0.79$	High Correlation
$0.8 \leq r \leq 1.0$	Very High Correlation

The Test Value (t-test)

To test the difference between the two means for independent samples; that is, to test if there is a significant difference in the RE facilities' declared areas and the computed actual areas they had damaged/affected.

$$t = \frac{(\bar{X}_1 - \bar{X}_2) - (\mu_1 - \mu_2)}{\sqrt{\frac{s_1^2}{n_1} + \frac{s_2^2}{n_2}}}$$

Interviews and Questionnaires

Since this paper was done during pandemic, face to face interviews were limited. Sets of survey questionnaires both for social and economic aspects of environment were designed so as to compensate the needed data for the study but has not prospered. Instead, a review based on random interviews among local residents was noted and questionnaires on ecological and economic status on both RE's were sent to and collected from their respective representatives. Appendix B shows sample of drafted survey questionnaire.

Areas of the Study

The Wind Farm is located in the northwestern section of Panay Island near the boundaries of Aklan and Antique provinces. The area consisting of 2,025 hectares lies within the jurisdiction of the Municipalities of Nabas and Malay in the Province of Aklan. The terrain is moderately rugged to rugged characterized by sharp ridges, steep to very steep slopes, v-shaped valleys and narrow valley floor with an elevation from 100 to 600 meters above sea level.

The Timbaban Hydropower Plant is situated in the south-central section of Aklan in Barangay Maria Cristina, Madalag, bounded on the nearby east by Balete, west by Province of Antique, north by Malinao and Banga, and south by Libacdao. Elevation is 79 to 600 meters above sea level.

Figure 6. Enlarged Map of Panay Island showing the location of Wind Farm in Nabas and Malay, and the Hydropower Plant in Madalag, Aklan. (Source, Google Map).

CHAPTER 4

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Data Quality and Assumptions

Renewable energy is no doubt, replenishable. Dilemmas: (1) its facilities during construction and operation maintenance during its lifecycle, (2) the materials for each machine/equipment to generate certain amount of energy, and (3) the storage due to uncontrollable/unpredictable supplies are things that these private companies tend to conceal which affect the ecology directly. Investment costs of each RE developers are highly confidential and the companies' officials cannot disclose the amount. Interviews with the Pollution Control Officers of both PEWEI and OEPGC were good enough to gather social, economic and ecological threats. Though most of the time, interviewees commended of the advantages of their projects. Asking about threats was an indicator to them that the interviewer was an opponent. Questionnaires sent by the author were rejected by PWEI Management, thus resulting to secondary data based on their submitted FLAg Compliance Annual Report. However, the Oriental Energy Corporation accepted and answered the questionnaires by the company owner's representative but the figures or amount on their investment were left blank.

By Using Land Cover Maps and Satellite Images

Changes in landscape caused by development were evident. Quantifying physical properties of actions, specifically measuring the length of roads, area of cleared land and changes to landscape features such as loss of wildlife habitat was also observed. PWEI wind farm is bordering the Northwest Panay Peninsula National Park (NPPNP) on the south and it is considered as near shore wind farm.

Plates 2 and 3. Aerial and terrestrial photos of the area affected by the development of wind farm in Nabas, Malay, Aklan.

SOURCE: Google Earth, 2021

Plate 4. Satellite image of portion of Panay Island showing the location of Northwest Panay Peninsula Natural Park

SOURCE: Google Earth, 2020

Figure 7. Land Cover Map 2015 Highlighting the NPPNP. Source: NAMRIA, 2015

Colored red spot is the Tree planting site assigned for PWEI which has a total area of 41 hectares for 461,650 forest tree seedlings and 8,000 fruit tree seedlings.

Figure 8. Shape files of fragmented landscape of wind farm area in Nabas and Malay, Aklan generated using CAD and ArcGIS.

Habitat fragmentation caused by new access roads and transmission lines which allow the introduction of invasive species.

Plate 5. Photo collage of Flora and Fauna within wind farm and Northwest Panay Peninsula Natural Park.

SOURCES: Magbiro, 2020 and Belarmino and Nadua, 2021

Patch Richness

Patch Richness is the simplest measure of landscape composition (McGarigal, 1995). It does not reflect the relative abundances of patch types.

For wind farm in Nabas, PR = 5. These are tabulated below:

Table 2. Patch Richness of Wind Farm in Nabas, Aklan.

Class Number	Patch Type
1	New access roads
2	Old or existing road before construction
3	Protected Area
4	Forest land
5	Alienable and Disposable Land

Plate 6. Satellite image of area where access roads and other development occurred in Maria Cristina, Madalag, Aklan.

SOURCE: Google Earth, 2020

Figure 9. Overlaid patches of Timbaban Hydropower plant in Land Cover Map 2015. Source: NAMRIA, 2015

Figure 10. Extent of the Access Road Development, Tunnelling and Other Construction Facilities for Timbaban Hydropower Power in Madalag, Aklan.

For Timbaban Hydropower project in Ma. Cristina, Madalag, PR = 5. These are shown in the generated shape file in Figure 10 and are tabulated below:

Table 3. Patch Richness of Hydropower plant in Madalag, Aklan.

Class Number	Patch Type
1	Access roads
2	River
3	Tunnel
4	Existing road within A & D
5	Timberland

Plates 7 and 8. Likтинon White Rocks in Brgy. Maria Cristina, Madalag, Aklan is part of Aklan River Watershed Forest Reserve. SOURCE: Zeta-Yap, 2015

Analysis on Affectivity of Technological Interventions

DTBird™

PetroWind procured DTBird Technology to lessen the mortality rate of birds that collide with the blades. DTBird is a self-working system that detects birds and can optionally take two independent actions to mitigate bird collision risk: the activation of warning sounds and/or the stoppage of the Wind Turbine (WTG). Potential and accidental bird collisions can be detected and recorded in real-time videos even at night. Discouraging sounds can be adjusted to target species and species-specific sounds can be applied. Automatic WTG stops and restart according to real-time bird collision risk evaluation. This features also data analysis platform.

The American Wind and Wildlife Institute (AWWI) contracted a third party, H.T. Harvey & Associates to conduct an independent evaluation of the DTBird detection/deterrence system. They used drones (eagle-like unmanned aerial vehicles) and *in situ* raptors to evaluate DTBird's ability to detect birds, and if reduction of risk of collisions with wind turbines are effective. According to their report, "DTBird successfully detected 63% of drones being used as surrogates for eagles. The system's ability to detect drones appeared to be reduced by sun glare and other variables." Likewise, "the deterrence rate in response to the warning/dissuasion signals was at least 52%, and as high as 83%. In many cases, responses from raptors were unclear." The report summed up stating that the system produced a large number of false-positive detections. "Detections occurred at closer and farther distances than expected. Both outcomes resulted in unnecessary deterrent signaling, which could adversely affect non-target wildlife and disturb facility neighbors and staff," (AWWI, 2018). PWEL's Pollution Officer, Ms. Rodelyn Ambagan conformed with the H.T Harvey and Associates' findings informing the author during an interview that DTBird has helped decreased the mortality rate to an average of nine (9) birds around the wind farm compared before which she preferred not to mention the number.

Locally, Provincial Environment and Natural Resources Office (PENRO) Aklan's Protected Area Management and Biodiversity Conservation Unit (PAMBCU) Head, Corazon Teodosio, accounted reports on the decrease population of flying foxes to and from Northwest Panay Peninsula Natural Park and Boracay Island, Malay, Aklan since the operation of wind farm started.

Plate 9. Overlooking Boracay from Nabas wind farms' turbines in Nabas and Malay Aklan

SOURCE: Ambagan, 2020

Plate 10. The PWEI Wind Farm in Nabas and Malay Aklan is between the Northwest Panay Peninsula Natural Park and Boracay Island.

Fishway

Fishway or fish ladder is a structure on or around artificial and natural barriers to facilitate diadromous fishes' natural migration as well as movements of potamodromous species.

Figure 11. Schematic drawing of a vertical slot fishway. (Source: Vazquez, 2011).

A fishway was constructed by OEPGC so that fishes can transverse from downstream of the weir going back upstream. According to the OEPGC's representative, the construction is about 11 million in pesos. The actual construction has been changed. The original perspective of the plan shown in Plate 11 was revised to Plate 12. Instead of straight and vertical parallel to the flow of the river, it has actually been constructed in a zig-zag and contained area.

Plate 11. Original perspective of Fishway at the weir. Plate 12. Actual implementation of Fishway

Plate 13. Photo collage of meeting with the OEPGC Staff, during tunnel construction and the built powerhouse

SOURCE: Zabal, 2016 and Magbiro, 2020

Boy Ryan B. Zabal of Aklan Forum Journal has posted on July 12, 2016 citing DENR in urging the OEPGC to stop ground operation including blasting which damaged naturally grown trees. China International Water and Energy Corporation (CWE) is a contractor of OEPGC in development and construction of the Timbaban Hydropower project. The OEPGC appealed to DENR for exemptions from penalties to the violations such as unlawful occupation and damages incurred in the protected areas and forest lands. The former Regional Executive Director of DENR Region VI, Jim O. Sampulna recommended the following to the DENR Central Office: Php 4.5 Million Pesos as fine for violations of sections 77 and 78 of Presidential Decree 705 (PDF 705) in “Cutting, Gathering, and or Collecting Timber or Other Forest Products without License” and Unlawful Occupation or Destruction of Forestland.”, amendment of Forest Land Use Agreement (FLAg), and to allow the DENR to conduct periodic evaluation and monitoring within the area. The reported damages within the National Greening Program (NGP) reforestation site during the construction of road network were 1,150 trees in the 2.3 hectares and 30 natural grown trees with a total volume of 95.39 cubic board feet aside from the deviation of road network which was not covered

by in the issued Special Tree Cutting and Earth Balling Permit by the Regional Director which only covered 107 standing trees. Until now, non-compliances of OEPGC are piling up. With the latest letter dated March 22, 2021 sent by the DENR PENRO Aklan, signed by the PENR Officer, Merlene B. Aborka enumerated the following:

“Result of said monitoring revealed that your company have not complied the following terms and conditions of your permit, to wit:

- 1. Submission of Annual Report;*
- 2. Submission of Comprehensive Development Management Plan which has already long overdue. Submission of the same should had made within six (6) months from the execution of the agreement;*
- 3. Delineation and demarcation on the ground of the boundaries of the FLAg area, also long overdue; and*
- 4. Implementation of 1,000 hectares Tree Replacement project which until now has not yet started. Sometime in 2016, this Office has sent you a letter reminding you thereof of your compliance along with a draft Memorandum of Agreement, Work and Financial Plan covering 120 hectares open area within Timberland as initial identified area for the said tree replacement for your review and comment. However, up to this date, we have not receive any opinion from your end regarding the matter.”*

The company is very complacent of all the warnings and memorandums and letters pertaining to their non-compliance. They are not also interested in deploying accredited People’s Organization in Madalag, Aklan.

Analyzing the cost for mitigation measures using advanced technology and engineering of both RE’s, the comparison was done by charting out the actual area affected with the aid of CAD and Arc GIS, area declared based on their submitted and approved Forest Land Use Agreement (FLAg) map by Forest Management Bureau Director and the amount of technology and engineering used and applied to help mitigate the adverse ecological effects of RE facilities they constructed. The unit of area is in hectares while the technology applied is in million pesos. That is, 1 million pesos per hectare was charted out to easily compare the difference.

The DTBird costs Php 1,357,438 each set including installation multiplied by 18 pieces (2 MW per WTG) for 36 MW wind farm equivalent to Php 24,433,884.00. Since 2016 to 2019, PWEI Nabas Wind Farm had generated a total of 481,802,974 MWh based on their reported Annual FLaG Compliance Report. The reflected area in their FLaG map was only 8.74 hectares compared to the area computed based on generated maps using aerial photo, CAD and GIS tools, which turned out to be 50.74 hectares.

However, OEPG’s Timbaban Hydropower Project is not yet operational as of this time. The fishway was given the amount of 11 million by the OEPGC owner’s representative. The declared area in their FLaG map was 78.95 hectares while the actual disturbed and affected is only 20.2383 hectares.

Figure 12. Bar Chart comparing the Timbaban hydropower plant and Nabas Wind farm on areas actual affected and declared in hectares and the technology applied in million pesos

It may be noted that based on DENR Administrative Order 2004-16 (DAO 2004-16), the annual rental fee for special use of forestland for energy projects is only Php 3000.00 per hectare and fraction thereof and to be increased cumulatively by 10% every year.

Evaluation of Ecological Impacts using Multi-Scale Model

In figure 6 of Chapter 3, the Multi-Scale Evaluation Model was shown describing from RE developments (wind farm and hydropower plant) to facility constructions as plant scale; wastes, air and water emission for river or local scale and operation and maintenance for watershed or regional scale. Under each scale, indicators of ecological loss were enumerated such as, but not limited to, environment pollution and soil erosion for plant scale; sediment deposition, noise, interferences, fish/bird habitat loss; and Net Primary Productivity (NPP) loss, carbon fixation and oxygen release loss including human habitat loss.

Ecological loss evaluation at a plant scale

Environmental pollution

For wind farm = 15,424,744

For hydropower plant = 5M

Soil Erosion

For wind farm = 25,220,660.90

For hydropower plant = 10 M

Ecological loss evaluation at the river/local scale

For hydropower plant, fish habitat destruction was considered as the Timbaban hydropower plant is a run-of-river without a reservoir to get the volume of bed-load sediment to compute sediment deposition. For wind farm, bird habitat loss will be accounted and estimated using the same method as with fish habitat loss:

For wind farm = 24,433,884.00

For hydropower plant = 11 M

Ecological loss evaluation at the watershed scale

Net primary productivity (NPP) loss, carbon fixation and oxygen release loss will be calculated by evaluating inundation by the market price method.

Net Primary Productivity Loss caused by Hydropower plant & Wind Farm

Using the Miami model (Lieth, 1975):

$$\mathbf{NPP}_{\text{Rain}(y)} = 3000(1 - e^{-0.000664\text{Rain}(y)}) \quad (5)$$

$$\mathbf{NPP}_{\text{Temp}(y)} = \frac{3000}{1 + e^{1.315 - 0.119 \text{Temp}(y)}} \quad (6)$$

$$V_{\text{NPP},j} = \left[\sum_{i=1}^4 (\text{NPP}_{ij} \cdot A_{ij}) - \sum_{i=5}^6 (\text{NPP}_{ij} \cdot A_{ij}) \cdot T \cdot \varepsilon_{\text{NPP}} \cdot P_{\text{coal}} \right] \quad (7)$$

where: Rain (y) is the annual rainfall (mm) and Temp (y) is the annual average temperature (deg C). NPP is expressed in grammes of dry matter per square meter per year. The author adjusted the NPP coefficient based on the land cover type in the region. ε is 0.354 based on Annual Mean ε defined by Dorman and Sellers (1989) for broadleaf and evergreen trees.

$V_{\text{NPP}}(\text{Php})$ is the value of net primary productivity loss in region j ; $\text{NPP}_{ij}(\text{gCm}^{-2}\text{yr}^{-1})$ is the net primary productivity reduction per unit area of land cover type i in region j ($i=1,2,\dots,6$) (i.e. forest, cropland, grassland, unused land, water area, and building land); A_{ij} (ha) is the inundation area of land cover type in region j ; T is the operation period of the hydropower project, which is approximately 50 years for Timbaban Hydropower Plant (Varun, et al., 2012); ε_{NPP} (%) is the calorific value ratio of standard coal and carbon; and P_{coal} (Php/ton) is the price of standard coal in the Philippines.

Based on tree inventory of Licensing and Permitting Unit, in PWEI wind farm, there were 2,216 naturally grown and planted trees that had been cut prior the development of the area. On the other hand, Timbaban hydropower plant area was surveyed after the cutting of trees. The accounted trees cut were 1,287. The average temperature for year 2015 was 28.08°C while the total rainfall/precipitation was

1,666.90 mm. Inundated area in Aklan was 7,039 hectares based on the study of Sinogaya & Paringit, 2017 published by UP Training Center for Applied Geodesy and Photogrammetry (TCAGP). The calorific value ratio for standard coal and carbon is to be multiplied by 0.238846 (sgs.ph) and the price of coal in the country was P4,100/ton (indexmundi.com). The Miami model calculates NPP based on regressions of temperature and precipitation against observed NPP. The author used the value of “ε” (plant biomass increment) adjusted to uniform globally and minimize error over all the sites.

For wind farm: 132.9 M

For hydropower plant: 53.07 M

Carbon Fixation and oxygen release loss

Using the Market Price Method (Li, et al., 2015):

Since all green plants sequester CO₂ and release O₂, and green plants construction and maintenance need investment, therefore the unit value of CO₂ sequestration and O₂ release depends on the cost of green plants construction and maintenance (Wang, et al., 2010).

$$M_{CO_2} = \left[\sum_{i=1}^4 (NPP_i \cdot A_i) - \sum_{i=5}^6 (NPP_i \cdot A_i) \right] \cdot T \cdot \alpha_{CO_2}, \quad (8)$$

$$M_{O_2} = \left[\sum_{i=1}^4 (NPP_i \cdot A_i) - \sum_{i=5}^6 (NPP_i \cdot A_i) \right] \cdot T \cdot \beta_{O_2}, \quad (9)$$

$$V_{CO_2 \& O_2} = P_{CO_2} \cdot M_{CO_2} + P_{O_2} \cdot M_{O_2}, \quad (10)$$

where: $V_{CO_2 \& O_2}$ (Php) = value of carbon fixation and oxygen release loss;

M_{CO_2} and M_{O_2} (g) = loss mass of CO₂ fixation and O₂ release;

P_{CO_2} and P_{O_2} (Php/g) = cost of CO₂ fixation and O₂ release per unit, based on the afforestation costing method;

α_{CO_2} (g) = mass of carbon dioxide fixed by 1 g of organic matter;

β_{O_2} (g) = mass of O_2 released by 1 g of organic matter

For wind farm: 124.794 M

For hydropower plant: 38.602 M

Human habitat loss

According to Li, et al., the monetary value of human habitat loss can be estimated as the cost of compensation for emigrant resettlement, estimated from the value of real estate in the region where the displaced people will be resettled using the recovering expense method:

$$V_{\text{human habitat}} = \text{Pop}_{\text{emigrant}} \cdot A_{\text{house}} \cdot P_{\text{house}} \quad (11)$$

where: $V_{\text{human habitat}}$ (Php) = the value of the loss of human habitat;

$\text{Pop}_{\text{emigrant}}$ (no. of person) = migrating population;

A_{house} (m^2 per capita) = average area of housing per capita in the resettlement place;

P_{house} (Php/ m^2) = house price in the resettled region in any given emigrant year.

For wind farm: 0

For hydropower plant: 16 M

Indicator analysis was done for deeper analysis by standardizing the six ecological loss indicators as presented above and their average values were taken according to the scales of the two RE systems.

Table 4. Values of ecological threats of wind farm and hydropower plant in million pesos

Ecological Threats	36-MW Wind farm	18-MW Hydropower
Pollution	15.42	5
Erosion	25.22	10
Habitat loss	24.43	11
NPP loss	132.9	53.07
CO2 fix. & O2 release loss	124.79	38.60
Human habitat loss	0	16

Figure 13. Graph comparing the two RE facilities' effects to environment at different scales in million pesos.

The results show that at the plant scale, pollution and erosion were almost the same level with the river scale on habitat loss. The NPP loss had the highest impact on watershed level for both wind farm and hydropower plant.

There was a slight fall on the amount when it comes to CO2 fixation and O2 release loss and likewise an overturn between the two RE facilities on human habitat loss effect.

Correlation Coefficient

Using Pearson's Correlation Coefficient formula to get the strength of relationship of both the hydropower plant and wind farm's mitigation and conservation efforts and the extent of their environmental damages by applying new technology, the correlation result is 0.577 which means moderate correlation.

$$r = \frac{n(\sum xy) - (\sum x)(\sum y)}{\sqrt{[n\sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2][n\sum y^2 - (\sum y)^2]}}$$

The Test Value (t-test)

To test the difference between the two means for independent samples; that is, to test if there is a significant difference in the RE facilities' declared areas and the computed actual areas they had damaged/affected.

$$t = \frac{(\bar{X}_1 - \bar{X}_2) - (\mu_1 - \mu_2)}{\sqrt{\frac{s_1^2}{n_1} + \frac{s_2^2}{n_2}}}$$

Table 5. Values considered for t-test for hydropower and wind farm

Landscape Affected	36-MW Wind farm	18-MW Hydropower
Declared Area in FLAg	8.74 hectares	78.95
Actual Area affected	50.74 hectares	20.24

Table 6. Measures of central tendency and variation for t-test

Variables	Area Declared in FLAg	Actual Area disturbed
N	2	2
Mean	43.845	35.489
Std. Deviation	35.105	15.251
Variance	1232.36	232.593

$$\text{Test value} = \frac{(\text{observed value}) - (\text{expected value})}{\text{Standard error}}$$

Using the significance value of 0.20 in “t Distribution” with an 80% confidence interval Table F in Appendix C, the critical values are -3.078 and +3.078 for a two-tailed since the variances are unequal with the degree of freedom (d.f) of 1. $H_0: u_1 = u_2$ $H_1: u_1$ is not equal to u_2 (claim).

$$t = \frac{(43.845 - 35.489) - 0}{\sqrt{(616.18 + 116.30)}}$$

$$t = 8.356 / 27.06 = 0.308$$

Figure 14. Critical and test values of the significance in difference of both RE facilities on declared areas vs. areas computed using GIS tools.

There is not enough evidence to support the claim that there is a significant difference in the declared areas and the actual areas of the hydropower plant and the wind farm. The null hypothesis that they are equal is cannot be rejected since the value $+0.308 < +4.303$. See Figure 14.

Socio-Economic Review

Survey among local residents in Barangays Pawa, Rizal and Unidos, Municipality of Nabas and Barangays Napaan, Poblacion and Sambiray, Municipality of Malay, Aklan was carried by handling survey questionnaires. Due to COVID pandemic, the target of 30 respondents was not achieved. Only 12 were gathered back. Instead, random interviews among locals and DENR employees compensated the information needed backed up by related reviews.

Based on interview with PWEI's pollution officer, PWEI assisted PAELDA (Pawa Agri-Tourism Livelihood and Development Association) in making handicrafts and sell to Kalibo market. PAELDA is a local People's Organization whom PWEI tapped to do the tree planting activities as required by the DENR. They also sponsored some elementary school scholars from nearby barangays as recipients and had donated school supplies as well during opening of classes. It can be recalled that on the watershed level on human habitat loss, wind farm has zero value which meant that they had cause no emigration or relocation of human settlements within the area.

Plate 14. Pawa Nabas Elementary School located within the PWEI's wind farm with a signage campaign not to cut more trees.

SOURCE: Magbiro, 2020.

PWEI, though champion when it comes to their social responsibilities, has obviously cut more trees than in OEPGC's hydropower plant in Madalag. The cost of

NPP loss and CO₂ fixation and O₂ release loss caused by the number of trees cut for the development of wind farm shown in Figure 13 was significant.

Plate 15. Overlooking Nabas wind farms' turbines from Boracay Island taken on March 11, 2020.

SOURCE: Magbiro, 2020

Boracay Island might be considered world class because of its white sand beach. Many tourists preferred to enjoy the beach but not the scenery around it. In some interviews, many tend to choose Palawan or Siargao when asked which is better than Boracay in terms of overall landscape and view.

In the case of Timbaban hydropower plant, community believes that there is more than hydropower project involved around the area. Other mineral extraction is suspected. It may be observed in Figure 12 the big difference of the area declared and was covered in the approved FLA_g than the actual area disturbed visible in the satellite and aerial photos. Chinese people who were sent from China were majority of workers during the construction of tunnels, access roads, power house, etc., whom according to the owner's representative were sent back to China before and the ECQ. The

company also did not intend to tap the services of the local People's Organization for their tree planting replacement obligation in the government. They are not willing to pay local groups to do the work for they look at them as "opportunists." They only hired one (1) local "forester" as what they called a high school graduate to take care of their little nursery at the back of their field office facility. In RA. 7156, or the "Mini-Hydroelectric Power Incentives Act, it is stated in the "Obligations of the Developer" that it "shall give priority in employment to Philippine nationals. It shall agree to employ qualified Filipino personnel in the operations and, after commercial production commences, shall undertake, upon prior approval of the OEA, the schooling and training of Filipino personnel for labor and staff position, including administrative, technical and executive management positions. It shall undertake a program of training assistance for OEA. Costs and expenses of training Filipino personnel for the developer's own employment shall be included in the operating expenses. Costs and expenses of a program of training for the OEA's personnel shall be borne on a basis to be agreed upon by the OEA and the developer."

It was also learned that their budget for environmental concerns on mitigating measures was included in the project's approved financial plan as a package in which they don't want to disclose the specific amount. It is also their obligation under the rules and regulation of DOE to "avoid hazards to life, health and waters pursuant to a safeguard the watershed area of its mini- hydro power plant system against illegal logging and other forms of forest destruction and/or assist the DENR in the enforcement of forestry rules and regulations or rehabilitation of the watershed area." Despite the non-compliance's of the OEPGC, in Table 8 below shows that it was only enlisted in the DOE's awarded hydropower projects last June 2020 when in fact it has started it construction since 2015.

Table 7. Awarded hydropower projects as of June 2020 in the province of Aklan.

Municipality	Name of Project	Company	Stage of Contract	Potential Capacity (MW)
Libacao	Main Aklan Hydroelectric Power Project	Sunwest Water and Electric Company, Inc.	Development	15.00
Libacao	Aklan River Middle West Tributary Hydroelectric Power Project	Sunwest Water and Electric Company, Inc.	Pre-development	2.40
Libacao	Aklan River Upper West Tributary Hydroelectric Power Project	Sunwest Water and Electric Company, Inc.	Pre-development	2.40
Libacao	Aklan River Lower East Tributary Hydroelectric Power Project	Sunwest Water and Electric Company, Inc.	Pre-development	3.00
Madalag	Timbaban Hydroelectric Power Project	Oriental Energy and Power Generation Corporation	Development	18.00
Malay	Aklan Pumped-Storage Hydroelectric Power Project	Strategic Power Development Corp.	Development	300.00

Source: DOE

CHAPTER 5

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

Ecological threats related to RE development is not that easy to assess. Different methods were employed to achieve the objective of this study. The author mainly focused on the landscape ecology of the subject areas in using GIS and CAD, there were a big difference in areas based on the result of rendering simulation model and the declared areas on their FLAg's. The Timbaban hydropower plant declared 390.10% in land area more than they actually disturbed contrast to the Nabas wind farm which declared 580.55% less than they actually damaged and deforested. Patch richness has increased from 3 to 5 classes due to new access roads and tunnels for Timbaban hydropower plant. Using multi-scale model in computing ecological impacts at different scale, it is found out that it is in NPP loss in watershed level marked the highest point where CO₂ fixation and O₂ release loss was the 2nd highest both for hydropower plant and wind farm. The *t*-test or test value was applied to test the significance of the difference in areas declared and areas computed from simulation model (GIS). In the significance value of 0.20, null hypothesis could not be rejected. Both RE's declared and computed (simulation model) areas were equal or no significant difference at all.

It is concluded that conservation activities imbedded in the contracts, specifically the tree planting replacement was not seriously taken by the OEPGC compared to PWEI. Under the "Obligations of the Developer" of Rule and Regulations on Filing Processing of Applications for Authority to Construct and Operate Mini-Hydroelectric Power Plants, "project description shall be submitted according to the guidelines set by the Department of Environment and Natural Resources (DENR) which should incorporate the measures that a project proponent intends to take to ensure that the adverse effects of the proposed project on the environment will be avoided if not minimized. It should also include a watershed development plan and the endorsement from the Local Government Unit." Since the start of the Timbaban hydropower plant until now, no watershed development plan, annual reports and Comprehensive Development and Management Plan (CDMP) was submitted and approved.

CHAPTER 6

RECOMMENDATIONS

ASEAN Center for Energy (ACE) reports that from discourses to policy actions, renewable energy is the center of attention. Recently, DOE is advancing to modify the 60:40 equity share requirement between local and foreign investors in RE projects to 100% foreign ownership. This of course is to attract more foreign investors. The propound policy revisions and re-alignments include the extension of duration of RE service contracts tenor to help reduce the tariff. The agency hopes to make it done through Circular. Constitutionally, exploration and development of state resources should be carefully reviewed and considered by the government if this has to go through legislative body. In undertaking the assessment of environmental impacts/ecological threats of both renewable energy developers in Aklan, it is recommended to evaluate effectiveness of conservation actions provided by RE developers by the DENR as well as identification of mitigation by proposing a review and restrictions in applicable laws. It is recommended to further study the biological effects on the river which entails watershed characterization and vulnerability assessment which might give a more precise results in assessing the impacts of hydropower plants' facilities development, operation and maintenance. A policy proposal which includes the following are based on the observations by the author during the conduct of the study: 1. Joint survey of developer and DENR for area under feasible study approved/issued authority or license by the DOE. 2. Procurement/acquisition of PENRO/DENR Regional Office of High Precision Drone (AUV) for accurate area survey. 3. Hiring of 3rd party validators/evaluators on technology application for mitigating measures such as DTBird and fishway. 4. Gaps among implementing PENRO, Regional office and central office of the DENR in compliance/complying requirements/payments, report, etc. must be resolved (developer goes directly to the DENR Central office to pay for penalties. No reports designated/memo instruction to PENRO of the status of the compliances). 5. Amendment of Land Classification Map.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX A. Salient Features of RA 9513, “Renewable Energy Act of 2008”

Section 6. Renewable Portfolio Standard (RPS). - All stakeholders in the electric power industry shall contribute to the growth of the renewable energy industry of the country. Towards this end, the National Renewable Energy Board (NREB), created under Section 27 of this Act, shall set the minimum percentage of generation from eligible renewable energy resources and determine to which sector RPS shall be imposed on a per grid basis within one (1) year from the effectivity of this Act.

Section 13. Government Share. - The government share on existing and new RE development projects shall be equal to one percent (1%) of the gross income of RE resource developers resulting from the sale of renewable energy produced and such other income incidental to and arising from the renewable energy generation, transmission, and sale of electric power except for indigenous geothermal energy, which shall be at one and a half percent (1.5%) of gross income.

To further promote the development of RE projects, the government hereby waives its share from the proceeds of micro-scale projects for communal purposes and non-commercial operations, which are not greater than one hundred (100) kilowatts.

Section 15. Incentives for Renewable Energy Projects and Activities. - RE developers of renewable energy facilities, including hybrid systems, in proportion to and to the extent of the RE component, for both power and non-power applications, as duly certified by the DOE, in consultation with the BOI, shall be entitled to the following incentives:

(a) Income Tax Holiday (ITH) - For the first seven (7) years of its commercial operations, the duly registered RE developer shall be exempt from income taxes levied by the national government.

Additional investments in the project shall be entitled to additional income tax exemption on the income attributable to the investment: *Provided*, That the discovery and development of new RE resource shall be treated as a new investment and shall therefore be entitled to a fresh package of incentives: *Provided, further*, That the entitlement period for additional investments shall not be more than three (3) times the period of the initial availment of the ITH.

(b) Duty-free Importation of RE Machinery, Equipment and Materials - Within the first ten (10) years upon the issuance of a certification of an RE developer, the

importation of machinery and equipment, and materials and parts thereof, including control and communication equipment, shall not be subject to tariff duties: *Provided, however*, That the said machinery, equipment, materials and parts are directly and actually needed and used exclusively in the RE facilities for transformation into energy and delivery of energy to the point of use and covered by shipping documents in the name of the duly registered operator to whom the shipment will be directly delivered by customs authorities: *Provided, further*, That endorsement of the DOE is obtained before the importation of such machinery, equipment, materials and parts are made.

(g) Zero Percent Value-Added Tax Rate. - The sale of fuel or power generated from renewable sources of energy such as, but not limited to, biomass, solar, wind, hydropower, geothermal, ocean energy and other emerging energy sources using technologies such as fuel cells and hydrogen fuels, shall be subject to zero percent (0%) value-added tax (VAT), pursuant to the National Internal Revenue Code (NIRC) of 1997, as amended by Republic Act No. 9337.

All RE Developers shall be entitled to zero-rated value added tax on its purchases of local supply of goods, properties and services needed for the development, construction and installation of its plant facilities.

This provision shall also apply to the whole process of exploring and developing renewable energy sources up to its conversion into power, including but not limited to the services performed by subcontractors and/or contractors.

(h) Cash Incentive of Renewable Energy Developers for Missionary Electrification. - A renewable energy developer, established after the effectivity of this Act, shall be entitled to a cash generation-based incentive per kilowatt hour rate generated, equivalent to fifty percent (50%) of the universal charge for power needed to service missionary areas where it operates the same, to be chargeable against the universal charge for missionary electrification;

(i) Tax Exemption of Carbon Credits. - All proceeds from the sale of carbon emission credits shall be exempt from any and all taxes; (RA No. 9513, Official Gazette, 2008).

APPENDIX B. Sample Survey Questionnaire

“Questionnaire”

By Valerie Joy D. Magbiro

For the Research Paper on *“Valuing ecological threats of renewable energy facilities in Aklan: Wind farm and hydropower plant”*

For environmental pollution:

1. How much is the total cost of investment in construction of the major waste water and solid waste treatment project due to construction of hydropower plant/wind farm? (include labor cost and materials, etc.)

For Soil Erosion:

During construction period, soil erosion occurs mainly in soil surface destruction, loss of arable land resources and loss of residual field soil

2. How much is the total cost of building a soil and water conservation project after or during the hydropower plant/wind farm construction/establishment?

For Ecological loss evaluation at the river/local scale:

3. How much is the total cost of fish protection/bird species protection project the RE developer has invested?

Ecological loss evaluation at the watershed scale:

4. How much is the total cost for tree or green plants construction and maintenance the company has invested so far?

5. How much is the total cost of compensation for emigrant resettlement estimated from the value of real estate in the region where the displaced people will be resettled?

6. How much is the inundation area (in hectares) covered inside the RE plant/facilities?

Inundation means "flooding" during rainy seasons.

Answered by:

Signature over printed name

Designation: _____

Company Name: _____

Date: _____

APPENDIX C. Table of Critical Values for *t*-test.

Table F		The <i>t</i> Distribution				
d.f.	Confidence intervals	80%	90%	95%	98%	99%
	One tail, α	0.10	0.05	0.025	0.01	0.005
	Two tails, α	0.20	0.10	0.05	0.02	0.01
1		3.078	6.314	12.706	31.821	63.657
2		1.886	2.920	4.303	6.965	9.925
3		1.638	2.353	3.182	4.541	5.841
4		1.533	2.132	2.776	3.747	4.604
5		1.476	2.015	2.571	3.365	4.032
6		1.440	1.943	2.447	3.143	3.707
7		1.415	1.895	2.365	2.998	3.499
8		1.397	1.860	2.306	2.896	3.355
9		1.383	1.833	2.262	2.821	3.250
10		1.372	1.812	2.228	2.764	3.169
11		1.363	1.796	2.201	2.718	3.106
12		1.356	1.782	2.179	2.681	3.055
13		1.350	1.771	2.160	2.650	3.012
14		1.345	1.761	2.145	2.624	2.977
15		1.341	1.753	2.131	2.602	2.947
16		1.337	1.746	2.120	2.583	2.921
17		1.333	1.740	2.110	2.567	2.898
18		1.330	1.734	2.101	2.552	2.878
19		1.328	1.729	2.093	2.539	2.861
20		1.325	1.725	2.086	2.528	2.845
21		1.323	1.721	2.080	2.518	2.831
22		1.321	1.717	2.074	2.508	2.819
23		1.319	1.714	2.069	2.500	2.807
24		1.318	1.711	2.064	2.492	2.797
25		1.316	1.708	2.060	2.485	2.787
26		1.315	1.706	2.056	2.479	2.779
27		1.314	1.703	2.052	2.473	2.771
28		1.313	1.701	2.048	2.467	2.763
29		1.311	1.699	2.045	2.462	2.756
30		1.310	1.697	2.042	2.457	2.750
32		1.309	1.694	2.037	2.449	2.738
34		1.307	1.691	2.032	2.441	2.728
36		1.306	1.688	2.028	2.434	2.719
38		1.304	1.686	2.024	2.429	2.712
40		1.303	1.684	2.021	2.423	2.704
45		1.301	1.679	2.014	2.412	2.690
50		1.299	1.676	2.009	2.403	2.678
55		1.297	1.673	2.004	2.396	2.668
60		1.296	1.671	2.000	2.390	2.660
65		1.295	1.669	1.997	2.385	2.654
70		1.294	1.667	1.994	2.381	2.648
75		1.293	1.665	1.992	2.377	2.643
80		1.292	1.664	1.990	2.374	2.639
90		1.291	1.662	1.987	2.368	2.632
100		1.290	1.660	1.984	2.364	2.626
500		1.283	1.648	1.965	2.334	2.586
1000		1.282	1.646	1.962	2.330	2.581
(z) ∞		1.282 ^a	1.645 ^b	1.960	2.326 ^c	2.576 ^d

^aThis value has been rounded to 1.28 in the textbook.

^bThis value has been rounded to 1.65 in the textbook.

^cThis value has been rounded to 2.33 in the textbook.

^dThis value has been rounded to 2.58 in the textbook.

Source: Adapted from W. H. Beyer, *Handbook of Tables for Probability and Statistics*, 2nd ed., CRC Press, Boca Raton, Fla., 1986. Reprinted with permission.

